

Modernising Electricity Distribution Grids in Spain: Assessing the Benefits of Digitalisation in the Context of the Spanish Recovery, Resilience, and Transformation Plans

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Executive Summary

Spain's energy industry is experiencing a massive transformation. This transformation is focused on energy production from renewable sources, energy efficiency, and the widespread introduction of electric vehicles (EVs), in line with key levers towards a decarbonised, electrified, decentralised, democratised, and digitalised energy sector, to achieve sustainable economic growth while mitigating the consequences of climate change. According to the Spanish National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) for 2030 (MITERD, 2020) the objectives are to boost the use of renewables to 42% of final energy consumption, improve energy efficiency by 39.5%, and attain a 74% proportion of renewable energy in electricity production.

The electricity sector, and particularly, electricity distribution grids will be the backbone of the key levers for the energy transition, as they are responsible for integrating the increasing share of renewable energy sources into the grid, facilitating the electrification of transport and buildings, and ensuring energy security, equity, and environmental sustainability. Within distribution grids, distribution system operators (DSOs), such as Iberdrola or Endesa Distribución (i-DE and e-distribución), are the main actors in charge of guaranteeing the quality of the electricity arriving to households and industries, as shown in Figure ES 1.

Distribution system operators operate under a complex regulated natural monopoly with trade-offs between user quality and investment costs. Determining DSO revenues is a challenging attempt owing to a wide range of factors involving operational and investment expenditures, budgetary limitations, and trade-offs between customers, regulators, and DSOs. Financial difficulties come as an outcome of the requirement to balance consumer expenses while safeguarding service quality, in addition to the continuing and upcoming obstacles of decarbonisation, electrification, decentralisation, and decarbonisation. As such, the remuneration of benefits for DSOs is a complex issue that requires special consideration and planning during the upcoming years.

Figure ES 1: Electricity and financial flows between Spanish conventional electricity sector stakeholders.

Current and future distribution grids are facing challenges that require grid modernisation. These challenges are related to the degradation and ageing of electric equipment in distribution grids, the penetration of self-consumers, the integration of EVs, and the lack of real-time measurements which impedes the prevention of abnormal situations in which the electricity demand may be over the maximum capacity of cables, as described in Figure ES 2.

Challenges in electricity grids are addressed by digitalisation, which is being used to improve energy efficiency, develop new products and services, and create innovative business models such as energy communities while enabling decarbonisation and the development of decentralised energy systems (Box 1).

Figure ES 2: Infographic of the challenges in present and future electricity grids.

Box 1: Key concepts of Digitalisation

- **Digitisation** is defined as the conversion from analogue information and processes into digital, facilitating data handling and storage, and fostering efficiency in operational processes.
- **Digitisation** is the increasing use of digital technologies such as sensors, drones, data analytics and robotics, in energy systems to unlock new benefits, and reduce technical costs and risks.
- **Digitisation delivers direct and indirect benefits** to multiple stakeholders and throughout the energy value chain.
- **Digitisation entails risks, and costs** due to its fast development, its early obsolescence, its carbon footprint, and the cyber-security and data privacy issues.
- Digitalisation presents unique challenges for its benefits quantification, due to its dual nature: **enabler of benefits and/or direct provider of benefits.**

Public and private investments are needed to leverage the opportunities and benefits of digital technologies while mitigating their risks and uncertainties. In the report developed by Deloitte, (Deloitte, 2019), it was estimated a global investment of 7 trillion € in electricity grids and 7 trillion € in renewables until 2040, although estimates of the volumes of investment required are quickly rendered obsolete by the speed and magnitude of the changes underway. This is a critical bottleneck in the digital transformation of the electricity sector where there is a need for private funding to accelerate the adoption of certain digital technologies and foster efficiencies and new business models.

Public investment is supported by European initiatives, funds, and actions. The European Green Deal and the EU Digitalisation Action Plan are ambitious initiatives to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and transform the EU into a more sustainable, resource-efficient, and circular economy, in which digitalisation plays a central role. These goals are addressed by different funding plans such as the NextGenerationEU Recovery Plan, which includes a €750 billion package of grants and loans, designed to support EU member states in their recovery efforts. Spain was assigned €69.5 billion. Furthermore, in June 2022, the grant allocation was revised upwards to €77.2 billion. In addition, in June 2023, the Council of Ministers approved the extension addendum for submission to the European Commission.

Within the Spanish Recovery and Resilience Plan, €525 M are specifically dedicated to fostering digital solutions to modernise distribution grids. Such funds are being distributed to the companies in charge of operating and maintaining the electricity grids, the so-called distribution system operators (DSOs), to modernise and digitalise their grids, as outlined the Royal Decree 1125/2021 (BOE, 2021), and as detailed in Figure ES 3. The €525 M funds will activate a total expenditure of € 1,050 million (M) of DSOs expenditures, half of it covered by the Spanish Recovery and Resilience Plan. These will be allocated to DSOs in line with their annual yearly allowed revenues, which depend on the number and type of customers served by each DSO.

Figure ES 3: Infographic of the €525 M funds allocated in the RD1125/2021, under Spain’s NRRP.

The benefits of public spending in distribution grids are not comprehensively exposed. According to the latest Eurobarometer for Spain (European Commission, 2023), more than one-third of Spanish citizens consider the recovery funds will not be effective to respond to current economic challenges. In addition, as expressed by the Spanish Organisation of consumers (OCU, 2022), only 11% of Spanish electricity consumers fully understood their electricity bill in 2021. Therefore, there is a need for a more systematic, systems-based approach to perform an ex-ante evaluation of the potential benefits provided by the €525 M funds. Such is the focus of the current report.

Distribution system operators will invest in different digital and conventional technologies. According to the most recent information from the Spanish National Markets and Competition Commission (CNMC, 2022b, 2022c), it is estimated DSOs will distribute their expenditures among : Control rooms and control elements necessary for the grid’s digitalisation (1. DESP_PRTR), elements for the digitisation and automation of networks: other technical distribution installations associated with smart grids, telemetry of digital assets, communication systems, and technical management systems (2. IBO_PRTR), and investments are made to develop and reinforce infrastructure for public electric vehicle charging points with a power capacity over 250 kW (3. V.E._PRTR). These technologies are illustrated in Figure ES-4.

Figure ES 4: Infographic of the key technologies to be adopted by distribution system operators under the funds.

Distribution system operators (DSOs) will significantly benefit from the investment in digital technologies, which impact on their key business areas. The impacts of digitalisation on DSOs are substantial across various business areas, including grid planning, construction and project management, grid maintenance, operation and control, and revenue maximisation. These impacts are illustrated in the figure below, which provides a breakdown of the calculated benefits of the funds on an annual basis, considering the calculations made in Section 5.

Figure ES 5 illustrates a breakdown of the estimated benefits resulting from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) funds for distribution system operators. The benefits are disaggregated based on key functionalities, highlighting the diverse areas where improvements and advancements are expected by the deployment of digitalisation technologies.

Multiple benefits are also affecting customers, electric vehicle owners, and society, as indirectly beneficiaries of DSOs digitalisation investments. Digitalisation of distribution grids improves reliability, reduces interruptions, provides capacity to integrate more renewables and electric vehicle charging points, and empowers consumers through platforms for flexible electricity trading and self-consumption.

Yet, existing cultural, economic, and technical uncertainties optimally hinder digitalisation and grid modernisation. One of the main issues is the unequal distribution of funding among distribution system operators (DSOs), which creates distributional differences. Additionally, adequate regulatory schemes need to be developed to incentivise digital investment while maintaining a suitable quality of supply. Metrics detailing the degree of digitalisation, observability, and smartness of DSOs' operation and planning should complement conventional indicators of quality and metrics of power losses. Regulation must also act to unlock data sharing while ensuring privacy. Finally, bureaucratic barriers hinder the integration of new chargers, and reforms are needed to facilitate their integration and connection, increasing dedicated governmental resources.

Comprehensive systems perspective and cost-benefit assessment are essential for effective and sustainable digitalisation in distribution grids. Next policies and projects need to be assessed from multiple stakeholders and multiple benefits perspective, due to the interconnectedness of the impacts of digitalisation and the central role of distribution grids in the energy transition. Thus, systems theory and modelling tools may facilitate the identification and quantification of benefits to unlocking the necessary digital investments in the electricity sector.

1. Introducing the energy transition and the need for digitalisation

Spain is currently experiencing a significant transformation in its energy system's structure. The deployment of renewable energies, which generated 42.2% of the energy mix in 2022, the adoption of energy efficiency measures, and the progressive integration of electric vehicles in the Spanish landscape, are clear cases of the current transition. Such transition, as represented in Figure 1., determines the future to be achieved to spur sustainable economic growth while contributing to mitigating the effects of climate change.

Figure 1. The **key levers of the energy transition**: Towards an energy industry that is more electrified, decentralised, democratic, and digitalised.

Energy must be generated in an ecologically responsible manner and supplied, under dependable and secure circumstances, at an accessible price for all consumers, to ensure an efficient, sustainable, and inclusive energy transition. The latter illustrates the ideal scenario, despite the difficulty of such objectives. For example, the Spanish national strategy against energy poverty (MITECO, 2019) states that in 2017, more than 8% of the Spanish population was unable to maintain a comfortable indoor temperature throughout the winter because of a lack of resources. This situation is becoming more challenging when facing rising electricity and gas prices because of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Therefore, to reach energy security, equity, and environmental sustainability, the energy transition is fostered, and supported by different **key levers**, as described in (Di Silvestre et al., 2018).

Decarbonisation

The **first key lever** is tailored to the decarbonisation target of reaching climate neutrality in 2050, as defined in the Spanish long-term strategic framework of energy and climate (MITECO, 2020). This goal is established in accordance with the Paris Agreement, which sought to limit the increase in global average temperature to 2°C. The most current assessment by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) states that such rapid climate change mitigation requires higher upfront costs (IPCC, 2023).

71% of Spanish citizens consider the money from the EU economic recovery plan should be mainly invested in the new green economy, (European Commission, 2021b).

Recently, at COP26 in Glasgow, it was agreed upon that by 2030, greenhouse gas emissions should be reduced by 45% compared to 2010 levels to maintain global warming below 1.5°C. This concern is also defined in the current ¹Spanish National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) (MITERD, 2020), which outlines the critical targets for the energy sector between 2021 and 2030:

- To increase the use of renewables to 42% of final energy consumption.
- To improve energy efficiency by 39.5%,
- To achieve a 74% share of renewable energy in electricity generation.

Electrification

If we are to achieve our decarbonisation objectives, we must renovate not only the power industry but also other energy-intensive sectors of the economy including transportation and buildings. Electrification, the second key energy shift lever, is viewed as the most effective and efficient approach to achieve this.

How are the transport, industry, and buildings sectors affected by electrification?

- In the transportation sector, the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) and the expansion of charging infrastructure are key to reducing noise, emissions, and pollution in local and global environments.
- Buildings are becoming more electrified and less reliant on fossil fuels for their energy, and the perspectives support this lever. For instance, energy supplied by heat pumps² is expected to rise 10 times from 2021 to 2030. This can reduce the energy required to heat, cool, and power buildings. Additionally, other technologies that may help with this include smart thermostats, effective insulation, and energy-efficient building designs and technology.

Decentralisation and democratisation

The **third** and **fourth key levers** within the energy sector transformation rely on the modernisation of the energy value chain, reshaping how the energy is produced, transmitted, and consumed. From the social perspective, users aim to participate actively in energy transactions, shifting from a passive to an active role in the energy sectors, deciding when to consume, and generate their electricity. This lever makes the energy sector more democratic and less reliant on large-scale and centralised power generation companies and entities. By empowering consumers with greater

¹ PNIEC update pending at the time of writing.

² Equipment used for heating and cooling, as well as for the supply of domestic hot water using electricity. It consists of a compressor, a condenser and an evaporator connected to a circuit through which a fluid circulates.

participation and control, they can play an active role in driving the shift towards renewable energy sources such as solar energy.

Self-consumption development can be visualised as multiple small generators distributed in space. This is the decentralisation lever, which is different from the conventionally centralised energy system in which massive power producing facilities, such nuclear or gas power plants, produce electricity far from consumption centres.

Decarbonisation, decentralisation, and democratisation taken together can result in a more just and environmentally friendly energy system that benefits customers and the environment. However, for all of the aforementioned levers to be effective, a further crucial lever within the energy transition must also be in place, and that lever is digitalisation, which is depicted as the foundation of Figure 1 and is further explained below.

Digitalisation

The ongoing energy transition is being driven by the **key enabling lever** of digitalisation in the energy sector. Just as our society employs smartphones to stay informed and streamline communication, the electricity sector is also modernising its value chain through the adoption of digital technologies. These technologies are being leveraged to improve energy efficiency, develop new products and services to monitor our energy consumption (for instance, smart meters), and create innovative business models such as energy communities and demand aggregators.

Digitalisation represents a **means** to achieve the decarbonisation of the energy sector (IEA, 2017) and is a key enabler to develop decentralised energy systems, which need communication, control, and automation to guarantee their correct performance. It is paramount to note that digitalisation is not a stand-alone process. It is a multi-step development that involves **digitisation**, the substitution of analogic hardware or routinary processes with digital assets (i.e., software or hardware), followed by **digitalisation**, which is the use of these digital assets to unlock new benefits, and ultimately, **digital transformation**, which involves a complete reimagining of business processes and models to fully take advantage of the benefits of digitalisation (J.Jung & G. Bengoechea, 2022).

In response to the need for decarbonisation, electrification, decentralisation, and democratisation, as well as to leverage the promising digitalisation opportunities, public funding has been allocated under the umbrella of Spain's National Recovery and Resilience Plan and the funds delivered by the Next Generation EU program (D'Alfonso, 2022). Investments are targeted at promoting the electrification of renewables, and accelerating the decarbonisation of the economy, as pointed out in (Joint, 2022). Particularly, part of these funds is dedicated to digitalising the electricity grid and modernising it to enable the integration of EVs in the upcoming years. Thus, such public investments are directly allocated to distribution system operators (DSOs), which are the companies managing and operating the Spanish distribution grids that arrive to households and industries.

Initially, these funds represent a positive means to activate new investments in innovative digital solutions such as new sensors to monitor the grids, modern control equipment in electric substations, and drones to monitor overhead cables, among others. These technologies offer promising potential for providing direct and indirect benefits for DSOs and society. However,

such benefits are often difficult to monetise, quantify or even measure due to the following reasons:

- Digitalisation may be simultaneously an enabler of benefits and a source of direct benefits. For instance, smart meters allow cost savings reducing inspections at households while enabling customers' self-consumption.
- Digital technologies rely on a combination of tangible and intangible assets mutually interdependent, which makes it difficult to quantify the benefits separately.
- Some benefits are the product of a long causal chain of effects in which identifying the links between an investment and a benefit may be a challenge. For example, investing in new cables to accommodate EVs can ultimately reduce the carbon emissions in road transport.
- Benefits affect different parts of the company such as the planning, customer attention, and operations departments, and therefore it is important to keep a holistic perspective to avoid double-counting.
- Finally, impacts can occur at different or the same time, while some benefits from digitalisation are only realised after having the required digital skills and data analytics tools.

Consequently, the magnitude of the benefits of this type of initiative may not be transparently described to the public, which produces uncertainty on how correctly EU funds are spent in Spain.

According to the latest Eurobarometer for Spain (European Commission, 2023), 36% of Spanish citizens consider the recovery funds will not be effective to respond to current economic challenges.

Considering the above, in this report, we want to raise the following **questions** about the recovery funds:

- *Why is the government providing €525 M funds directly to DSOs? What is the context behind that action? Why do these companies need funds to digitalise the grids?*
- *How are these funds affecting consumers? what are the potential benefits, risks, and costs such projects will bring to each stakeholder?*

To answer the above questions, we need to provide context on the structure and motivation of the Next Generation EU program funds and on how they affect the Spanish electricity sector. Moreover, it is necessary to define and clarify the complex role of the companies receiving the specific funds to digitalise the electricity grids, the DSOs, in the Spanish context. Having such a background, a deeper analysis of the benefits, costs, risks, and opportunities unleashed by digitalisation and such funds in the energy sector can be carried out. This report provides such an analysis to clarify the multiple benefits of public funds, from a multiple-stakeholders approach.

This is, in fact, the main purpose of this report, which will be structured as follows:

- **Section 2** provides an overview of European and Spanish regulations encompassing the Spanish National Recovery and Resilience Recovery Funds. Then we aim to investigate how this money may impact different stakeholders and for this, an understanding of past, current, and foreseen digitalisation of the electricity sector is fundamental.
- Such information is presented in **Section 3**, where an overview of the Spanish electricity sector and the implications of the key levers described in Figure 1, are provided.
- To provide a clear description of digitalisation technologies and their applications in distribution grids, **Section 4** is presented.
- Next, the assessment of the benefits derived from the expenditure of 525M Spanish National Recovery and Resilience Recovery Fund will be performed in **Section 5**, following a multi-stakeholder approach.
- To conclude, in **Section 6**, a discussion on the usefulness of these funds to foster digitalisation is provided. Next, the potential next steps to improve further studies and untap the benefits of digitalisation in electric distribution grids are highlighted.
- Finally, **Section 7** provides the references consulted to develop this report.

2. Funding digitalisation in the Spanish energy sector: An overview of European and national initiatives

Spanish electricity consumers are seeing a volatile and rising electricity bill, despite the multiple efforts of the Spanish government to reduce prices (e.g., reduction taxes on electricity). This is a complex, and multi-fold issue, which claims for structural measures and modernisation of the energy sector and industry, starting with reducing fossil fuels dependence while guaranteeing that the energy produced from renewables is stable and reliable, and its benefits can be translated to the customers.

The latter problem is not unique to the Spanish context, but it is also a central concern for the European Commission (EC), which also intends to address decarbonisation, decentralisation, decarbonisation, and democratisation with several policy initiatives.

The EU Green Deal (2019-2050)

The mainstream European Union (EU) initiative is the EU Green Deal. The European Green Deal represents the EU's ambitious plan to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and to turn Europe into a more sustainable, economical in resources, and circular economy. The EU Green Deal triggers €1.8 trillion in expenditures, or as 10.47% of the European Union's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2021. This plan includes a series of legislative initiatives, investment plans, and policy measures described in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The EU Green Deal. Source: (European Commission, 2021a).

To enable the ambitious goals described in the EU Green Deal, digital technologies and the modernisation of energy systems are considered major allies.

EU Digitalisation Action Plan (2022-2050).

Digitalisation cannot be left to the market alone. Issues such as security, privacy, and consumer protection must be considered while guaranteeing digital technologies effectively enable the energy transition and provide benefits to all stakeholders. Consequently, in 2022, the EC

decided to launch the EU Action Plan to digitalise the energy system. The EU Digitalisation Action Plan focuses on five areas:

- **Sharing data among stakeholders:** data provides value, and it is essential that consumers and enterprises can access such data to capture the value. For instance, data from electric appliances is important for small consumers to avoid peak electricity prices and to identify standby loads to improve energy efficiency.
- **Empowering citizens through participation tools and reskilling pathways:** this corresponds to the democratisation objectives, which require citizens to have enough digital and technical skills to participate in energy markets.
- **Scaling up the deployment of digital solutions:** some of the digital solutions such as the transaction of energy among neighbours in a building are still not mature. The regulation needs to facilitate their upscaling.
- **Enhancing cybersecurity:** avoiding cyber-attacks is the goal of this item, which is a growing concern in the energy sector to guarantee the continuity of supply and data privacy of consumers.
- **Supporting climate-neutral solutions for digital technologies:** fostering a more sustainable energy system by using the benefits of digital technologies, therefore, the environmental impact of the energy consumed by digital technologies, added to the impact of manufacturing hardware, needs to be properly controlled and monitored.

*“To end the EU's dependence on Russian fossil fuels and tackle the climate crisis, our energy system requires a deep transformation, **in which digitalisation plays a central role.**” (European Commission, 2022)*

Within the EU Digitalisation Action Plan, as well as within the EU Green Deal, the EC envisions performing a series of actions using legislative initiatives, investments, and coordination with the Member States in the coming years. These countries will make use of the available EU funding instruments, such as the **NextGenerationEU (NGEU) Recovery Plan**, to fast-forward the energy transition.

NextGenerationEU Recovery Plan (2021-2027).

The **NGEU Recovery Plan** is a set of funding procedures designed to aid EU Member states to channel funding into their economy, in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian invasion of Ukraine. The plan includes a €750 billion package of grants and lends, designed to fund EU member states in their recovery efforts, with a motivation on investments in key economic areas such as decarbonisation, healthcare, education, social infrastructure, and, importantly, **digitalisation**. Within the European Funds for Recovery and Resilience, over 20% of the funds have been allocated for digitalisation, which is considered essential for the future of the economy (Joint, 2022).

To access the NGEU funds, Member States had to submit their National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs) to the European Commission. Here, Spain's NRRP was assigned one of the largest funds by the European recovery instrument with €69.5 billion in non-repayable grants, which represents 9.6% of the entire RRF, or 5.6% of the country's gross

domestic product (GDP) in 2019. Furthermore, in June 2022, the grant allocation was revised upwards to €77.2 billion.

The above is an unprecedented and significant investment, which would be extended once the application submitted by the Government to the European Commission in June 2023 has been approved. However, we may ask the following questions:

- ❓ *What are the specific investments and reforms to be developed under the umbrella of the Spanish NRRPs?*
- ❓ *How digitalisation of energy systems, and particularly the electricity sector, is included in the Spanish NRRPs?*

To answer the previous questions, we must dive into the structure and specific components of the Spanish NRRP.

Spain's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) (2021-2027)

With the goals of boosting economic activity and job creation to offset the COVID pandemic's short-term effects, supporting the economy's broad structural transformation, and directing the transition to a more sustainable and resilient growth model, Spain's NRRP consists of numerous measures such as investments and reforms.

Firstly, addressing the specific economic challenges, Spain's NRRP identifies four lines of action: green transition, digital transformation, social and territorial cohesion, and gender equality in which a total of **211 measures**, of which **102** are **reforms** for the 2021-2023 period, are aggregated. Likewise, these measures are divided over **10 policy levers (PLs)** or key actuation areas, as described in Figure 3. Such levers include **30 components**, which address specific actuation plans for the economy.

Figure 3. Breakdown of the 10 lever policies of Spain's National Recovery and Resilience Plan. Source: (D'Alfonso, 2022).

The energy transition appears across the entire NRRP, due to the potential of the energy sector to modernising other economic sectors and contribute to their competitiveness. It is noted that

the lever that addresses, more specifically, the key levers in the energy system is the third policy lever. Thus, PL III will be the focus of this study.

The PL III policy lever is dedicated to fostering the development of a decarbonised, competitive, and efficient energy sector, allowing the channelling of significant private investment, reducing technological and regulatory uncertainty, and leveraging the Spanish renewable potential to strengthen competitiveness.

This LP is further subdivided into 4 components (C7, C8, C9, and C10) targeting particular areas of interest for the Spanish roadmap toward a fair and inclusive transition, as defined in the National Plan of Energy and Climate (PNIEC) (MITERD, 2020). These components are defined as follows:

- C7: Deployment and integration of renewable energies.
- **C8: Electrical infrastructure, promotion of smart grids, and deployment of flexibility and storage.**
- C9: Roadmap for renewable hydrogen and its sectoral integration.
- C10: Fair energy transition strategy.

PL III is not an individual measure but belongs to a set of actions aggregated into the Spanish strategic project for economic recovery and transformation, focused on renewable energies, renewable hydrogen, and energy storage systems, the so-called PERTE ERHA, as described in (Gobierno de España, 2022). However, since the interest of this study is to assess the benefits, costs, risks, and opportunities to invest in and foster digitalisation in electricity grids, we focus on **Component 8** in this study.

C8: Electrical infrastructure, promotion of smart grids, and deployment of flexibility and storage

Component 8 represents 1.96% of Spain's NRRP, with a budget of €1365 million. This is described in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Infographic of the €525 M funds allocated in the RD1125/2021, under component 8 of Spain's NRRP.

As explained in the figure, €525 million will be invested in the modernisation of electricity distribution grids. Such funds are being distributed to the companies in charge of operating and maintaining the electricity grids, the so-called **distribution system operators** (DSOs), to modernise and digitalise their grids, with a specific goal of deploying 30 innovative projects in place by the end of 2023. This investment opportunity can be found on the Royal Decree 1125/2021 (BOE, 2021).

Assigned public funds are distributed differently among DSOs, who can access an amount proportional to their annual allowed revenues. These revenues result from the grid access charges consumers pay in their electricity bills, which are updated by the energy market regulator in every regulatory period. Therefore, the larger the DSO's annual revenues and the higher the number of customers and electricity delivered through their electric assets, the larger the allocation of funds will be. For instance, we can observe such distribution over the three major Spanish DSOs in Table 1, together with the stated amount of the €525 M recovery funds to be used by DSOs between 2021 and 2023.

Table 1. Distribution activity compensation by the company and funds granted to the three major DSOs by several customers.

Company	Allowed revenues in 2017 (in €)	Share of the sector in 2017 (%)	Declared funds to be used by DSOs (2021-2023) (in €)	Link to source
Endesa Distribución Eléctrica, S.L.	2,092,491,905	38.93%	206,000,000	e-distribución
Iberdrola Distribución Eléctrica, S.A.	1,733,235,842	32.24%	168,500,000	I-DE
Unión Fenosa Distribución, S.A.	756,439,703	14.07%	73,000,000	UFD
3 Major DSOs funds	4,582,167,450	85.24%	447,500,000	50%
3 Major DSOs expenses			895,000,000	100%
Total, DSOs expenses			1,050,000,000	100%

The legislation regulates that the funds allocated will amount to up to 50% of the actual annual investment spent by the beneficiaries of the aid, the remainder being reimbursed from their annual revenues, coming from the regulated part of the electricity bills each consumer pays. Thus, total expenditures for the three major DSOs will reach €895 M, **with a total expenditure of all DSOs around €1,050 M, half covered by Spain's NRRP.**

This legislation regulating these funds stipulates that the stakeholders who receive funds, the electricity DSOs must undertake projects that involve either (A) innovative digitalisation initiatives for distribution networks or (B) electric infrastructure to accommodate the development of electric EV charging points at public access.

 Why is it necessary to digitalise the electricity distribution grids? What exactly does “digitalise” mean in this context? What is the purpose? What problems hinder investments in digitalisation and new charging points?

As we know from Figure 4, DSOs will be the beneficiaries of investments aimed at digitalising the grid and at reinforcing the grid to enable the connection of new EV charging points.

Both problems involve regulatory, economic, technical, social, and ecological implications. Section 3 offers information to help readers understand the significance of DSOs in the past, present, and upcoming power systems with the objective to bring out some understanding on this subject matter. Subsection 3.1 describes the role of DSOs within the electricity sector from a user-centric perspective. Next, in subsection 3.2, we explore the costs and revenues of DSOs from a systems perspective. Then Subsection 3.3 highlights the DSO challenges, regarding electrification and the deployment of EV charging infrastructure, and describes the opportunities offered by digitalisation levers. Finally, subsection 4 highlights digitalisation technologies and the need to deploy digital solutions in distribution grids.

3. The Spanish electricity sector: Current levers and future nexus energy-digital

The Spanish electricity sector represents 0.8% of the GDP, includes more than 180,000 direct, indirect, and induced jobs, and has more than 28 million connection points (Aelec, 2023). In addition to its relevance, this sector is one of the most complex due to its high degree of specialisation, its high number of stakeholders of different kinds, and its multiple dimensions, regulatory, technological, economic, social, and environmental as described in (Bale et al., 2015). This complexity is increasing rapidly with the energy transition challenges and the key levers described in Section 1, which are supported by technological development and, particularly, digitalisation. Under this complexity, the Spanish energy customers are expected to be the main actors in the energy transition by participating in new markets, using renewable energies, and taking advantage of the use of digital technologies in electricity (MITERD, 2020). However, is this possible if, according to the Spanish Organisation of consumers (OCU, 2022), **only 11% of Spanish electricity consumers fully understood their electricity bill in 2021?** There is a need to tackle that issue and reduce the energy divide before pursuing the energy-digital transition.

3.1. The Spanish electricity sector and its key stakeholders

The whole process of power generation, transmission, distribution, and consumer delivery falls under the umbrella of the electrical industry, which is made up of several operations and procedures. These are described in Figure 5, which represent the conventional display of the electricity value chain. Such overview represents the unidirectional generation of electricity, which has been traditionally carried out by power plants using, nuclear energy, hydropower, coal, natural gas, or other fossil fuels. Then since energy must first be transferred across great distances by grid lines or cables. Regarding such lines, we may classify them regarding their operating conditions, which may be transmission voltage (above 132 kV), high voltage (between 132 kV and 36 kV), medium voltage (between 36 kV and 1 kV), and low voltage (under 1 kV). The latter grid lines are then used transmit electricity, which reaches subsequently several high voltage customers and electrical substations, where it is converted to lower voltages and given to local power distribution networks. These are the cables reaching our houses, commonly at 230 V.

Figure 5. Electricity and financial flows between stakeholders in the Spanish conventional electricity sector.

In Figure 5, customers receive their electricity, which is regularly paid as reflected in their electricity bills. In this schema, customers are represented in low voltage since, in Spain, more than 96% of consumers are connected to low voltage, according to the Spanish National Markets and Competition Commission (CNMC, 2022a).

Customers in high, medium, and low voltage pay mainly for two concepts: the electric energy they consume, and the use of the transmission and distribution grids, which enable the transmission of electricity. Regarding electricity, energy retailers, and large consumers are the ones allowed to purchase electricity from generators in a wholesale market (the so-called pool market). Additionally, energy retailers are allowed to sell this electricity to end-users through a variety of rates and contracts. Regarding electricity bills, we can distinguish two main types of electricity contracts in Spain:

- a) **Regulated contracts:** this type of contract is uniquely offered to low voltage customers with a contracted power of less than 10kW (which means the aggregated power of all their appliances if used simultaneously is equal to or less than 10kW). Companies in the regulated market sell energy exclusively at the regulated tariff set by the government, which is called the voluntary price of small consumers (PVPC). In this type of tariff, the price is variable, depending on the wholesale electricity market, which varies depending on the season of the year, the day of the week, and the hour of the day³. The CNMC sets a profit margin for providing this regulated service.
- b) **Liberalised market contracts:** this kind of contract is defined entirely by the energy retailers. Prices can be fixed or variable depending on the wholesale market price and the strategies of the energy retailer.

As anticipated before in Figure 5, both a) and b) customers will pay for their electricity consumption (kWh) and access to the transmission and distribution grids, as well as for the services of energy retailers, among other concepts such as tolls and taxes. To provide an order of magnitude, during 2021, the average cost of electricity for customers in the regulated market described in a), represented 57% of the total electricity bill, where 4% was the margin of the energy retailers and 39% was linked to access charges and tolls, including payment for the transmission and distribution services (CNMC, 2022a).

After subtracting the margins of energy retailers, money and taxes received are distributed across the different stakeholders that generate power, own and operate transmission grids, own and operate distribution grids, and regulate the whole electricity market.

Firstly, power generation companies are remunerated according to the energy offered in the wholesale market in a competitive environment where different companies compete to sell their energy. A different remuneration is assigned to transmission and distribution grids. This is regulated by the CNMC, which defines the access charges for electricity consumers. Access charges have two main components that reflect maximum power demand (defined as contracted power in low voltage) and energy consumption. On the one hand, as energy demand increases over time, it will influence the total amount of energy transmitted by using the system. The greater the value of the instantaneous power demanded from the grid, on the other hand, the more revenue paid to transmission and distribution stakeholders, since they must update

³ With the progressive inclusion of forward prices from 2024, according to the new PVPC regulation approved in June 2023.

their grids, cables, and electric equipment to be ready in case a consumer wants to demand power close to its maximum expected values. In other words, if the cables providing the electricity to an industry or house have a certain power capacity, for instance, 30 kW, and suddenly we demand 50 kW, cables may suffer overheating, so we will be charged accordingly to pay potential grid extensions and capacity additions to meet the new power demand of 50 kW. This situation is common when new customers demand their connection to the grid, which may not have enough power capacity.

The role of transmission system operators (TSOs)

In Spain, as in other European countries, the transmission grids are managed by a national company, the transmission system operator (TSO), which owns, operates and maintains the high voltage grids. As in the case of distribution networks, natural monopoly conditions are assumed. In the case of transmission networks, only one company operates the very high voltage networks because, due to high investment costs and other market and environmental barriers, no other company could enter the market to carry out this activity. The regulator defines under what circumstances the TSO earns revenues and what its duties and obligations are. Electricity transmission is legally separated from distribution, retail and generation, and is carried out by Red Eléctrica de España (REE).

The role of distribution system operators (DSOs)

Scrolling to the right in Figure 5, we can find the activity of electricity distribution, in charge of connecting new customers, performing the maintenance of the grid, and ensuring the quality of supply is optimal. The distribution activity is also defined as a natural monopoly, in which few companies are distributed through the Spanish territory operating the high, medium, and low voltage grids, where most customers are connected. This is done by distribution network operators (DSOs), in charge of guaranteeing that the electricity arriving to households and industries is provided with the required quality of supply, minimising the duration and frequency of interruptions. According to the CNMC information from 2022, there are 333 DSOs in Spain. However, there are 5 which stand out regarding the number of consumers throughout the Spanish territory, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Distribution of the largest distribution system operators (DSOs) by number of customers in Spain. Source: (Alcanzia, 2023)

3.2. Revenues and costs structure in distribution system operators

DSOs’ tasks are distributed among different business areas characterising their activity, which are:

- **Grid planning:** forecast, identification, design, and implementation of strategies to improve the reliability, security, and efficiency of electricity distribution grids.
- **Construction and project management:** activities related to the physical implementation of the grid planning and deployment of new electric assets.
- **Grid maintenance:** a set of tasks aimed at keeping the grid in good operating condition, detecting, and fixing any faults, and preventing any major failures or blackouts.
- **Grid operation and control:** set of activities to ensure that the grid operates safely, reliably, and efficiently, by maintaining the power quality within acceptable limits.
- **Customer service:** activities aimed at understanding and meeting the needs, applications, and expectations of the customers, such as applications for new connections.
- **Revenues maximisation:** activities dedicated to increasing the value generated by the DSO's activities, by optimising the revenue streams from the charges.

DSOs provide an important service to customers, face significant yearly investment costs to maintain the grids and the electrical equipment, and are sensitive to opportunistic behaviours. This means that, due to their monopolistic position, they can influence the quality and affordability of the electricity supply. That is the reason why this is a highly regulated activity, where the Spanish public administrations, using the CNMC, must ensure adequate revenues for the DSOs by balancing a trade-off between the necessary benefits for its economic viability and reduced charges for the users of the service, as explained in (TG San Román, 2007).

Charges are set yearly by CNMC, considering the anticipated operational costs and investment requirements performed by the Distribution System Operators (DSOs). These charges, known as access charges, are further categorised into two components: a connection charge and a usage charge, which vary based on the voltage level and contracted power. Furthermore, a mechanism known as time discrimination is applied, introducing varying temporal access charges over different periods.

Figure 7. Disaggregated net revenues of DSOs and identification of a set of key factors affecting costs and benefits.

Considering the complexity of the costs and revenues structure of the DSOs, a cause-effect diagram is provided in Figure 7 and Figure 8, to illustrate the dynamic links between the

elements driving grid charges, revenues, and costs of the distribution grid operators. Firstly, in Figure 7 we can appreciate the main elements affecting the yearly revenues, operating costs, and investment costs of DSOs per year. Benefits increase with access charges and energy consumption, while operation costs increase with the expenditures in maintenance and new equipment, respectively. Here, (+) means directly proportional, and (−) represents indirectly proportional relationships. For example, a link is indirectly proportional (−) if, when operational costs increase, net revenues decrease.

Figure 7 provides a systems perspective of DSOs’ business models. However, the picture is extremely simplified, since each of the costs and benefits is affected by the state of the electrical assets, the regulatory constraints, and the evolution in the number of customers, among other variables. This is expressed more comprehensively in Figure 8, in which a causal loop diagram identifies the most relevant cause-effect relationships driving the costs and benefits of DSOs.

Figure 8. Cause-effect diagram of a selection of costs and benefits of distribution system operators in the Spanish context.

The above diagram includes links, variables, and delays, which define the dynamics of DSOs from a systems perspective. The parts of this diagram are explained, in detail, in the following lines.

About DSO’s revenues per year and DSO’s allowed revenues for next years.

- **Access charges** are calculated yearly depending on the **allowed retributions** the regulator (CNMC) assigns to the DSO for the next year.
- The regulated remuneration in a given year is made up of remuneration for investments and operating and maintenance expenses foreseen for that year. In addition, the remuneration includes a system of incentives to reduce losses and improve quality. The methodology is set out in CNMC Circulars 5/2019 (for TSO) and 6/2019 (for DSOs). As noted above, transmission and distribution tolls are set so as to provide sufficient revenue to cover the expected network costs for the year (including possible cost deviations from previous years).

- Consequently, the remuneration obtained is affected by the costs experienced by the DSOs and their quality of service during the previous years. Incentive regulation penalises high costs and low quality of supply and compares DSOs with other distribution companies. The purpose of this system is to promote the modernisation and efficiency of regulated entities by simulating a competitive environment (TG San Román, 2007).

About DSO's operational costs

- The **number of consumers** affects the **operational costs**, since the higher the energy demand, the higher the energy losses, and the higher the costs of billing and phone attention, reading of meters and metering equipment, and management of non-payment.
- Additionally, **operational costs** will increase when cables and electric equipment are operated over their maximum capacity. In the same manner, a water tank may collapse when the water level reaches or rises above the maximum, and power levels over the maximum capacity may increase the probability of failure of grid assets.
- **Operational costs** are also affected by technical obsolescence. The more closely an electrical connection arrives to the limit of its usable life, the more likely it will fail to perform. Thus, corrective maintenance costs will arise when it fails and preventive maintenance costs before it does.
- Preventive maintenance is the traditional tool of DSOs to tackle the technical obsolescence of cables, keeping grid assets alive using periodic visits, inspections, and repairs.
- As illustrated by the cause-effect diagram, operating costs and new grid assets can extend the lifetime of assets and, thus, increase the quality of supply.

About DSO's investment costs

- Often, DSOs have a grid planning department to determine how their grid lines and assets are expected to evolve and to identify the optimal investments that can reduce power losses, enable the connection of new customers in the future, and reinforce areas where the number of failures is significant. Thus, planning engineers identify such key areas and plan future investments.
- Regarding investments, we can distinguish between compulsory investment and Investment at the DSO's initiative. The former is dedicated to the connection of new customers and producers, including housing developments, while the latter represents the expansion of existing capacity, and the restoration of grid assets not adapted to current technical requirements, among others.

Figure 9. Balancing investment costs and costs of interruptions for customers. Source: (TG San Román, 2007).

There exists a fine equilibrium in the costs and benefits of DSOs, as we can derive from Figure 9. This system is influenced by the objectives of customers, the regulator, and the DSO. Customers strive for the highest possible level of quality, aiming to minimise interruptions and urging the DSO to deliver optimal service at the most competitive price. However, as enhancing service quality necessitates increased operational costs and investments for the DSO, there exists a trade-off between costs for customers and the DSOs.

Another trade-off can be observed between the DSO and the regulator. While the former may prioritise replacing expensive, large-scale electrical equipment to improve overall revenue allowances and enhance service quality, the regulator may hold a different view due to concerns about potential customer charge increases. In contrast, the regulator may have the goal of driving DSOs to invest in less costly technologies that can simultaneously improve the quality of the power supply while maintaining stable prices for customers. This is one of the driving forces behind regulators, which generally aim to promote the use of new technologies and solutions.

We could be asking if the specific problem can become any more difficult at this point. The current and forthcoming difficulties associated with grid modernisation, electrification, decentralisation, and carbon reduction increase the need for DSOs and final customers to take on leadership responsibilities.

3.3. Distribution grids challenges in present and future electricity grids

The grid is evolving towards an unobserved scenario, where intermittent and stochastic renewables will substitute fossil fuels, distributed generation (smaller and closer to customers) is replacing centralised and large-scale power plants (Ackermann et al., 2001), distribution grids, which now have to face new generation and increasing demand due to electric vehicles and electrification trends (shift from natural gas to electricity to boil water at households). In addition, differently from the high voltage transmission lines, medium and low voltage distribution grids are not monitored in real-time. This has been because a failure in high voltage is highly critical and affects many consumers, while a failure in distribution grids is less critical, and electricity can be restored easier. Thus, generally, the traditional strategy has been to invest, when there is a failure, in a new cable or substation. This strategy must be updated when

distribution grids are facing more challenging electric conditions and new loads are connected to them.

In Figure 10, a selection of technical challenges in the contemporary and future electricity grid is presented, focusing on the perspective of distribution grids, where most new customers (e.g., EVs, and self-consumers) will be connected, being the base for electrification, decentralisation, and democratisation.

Figure 10. Infographic of the challenges in present and future electricity grids.

These challenges are related to the degradation and ageing of electric equipment in distribution grids, the penetration of self-consumers, the integration of EVs, and the lack of real-time measurements which impedes the prevention of abnormal situations in which the electricity demand may be over the maximum capacity of cables. **These challenges are considered in the legislation regulating the €525 million recovery funds**, which provide funding to DSOs for undertaking projects on innovative initiatives for distribution networks and EV charging infrastructure development. The previous challenges are further detailed next.

Natural disasters and climate-related events

Safeguarding the electricity sector from interruptions and power outages becomes critical due to climate change's impact on the electricity system, including generation potential, network resilience, and demand patterns (IEA, 2021). Recent events, like the power outages caused by wildfires in Spain (March 2023), highlight the vulnerability of electricity systems to climate hazards. In response, the Spanish electricity grid is increasing the use of underground lines, which are less affected by natural disasters. (Deloitte, 2021).

Stress and ageing in the electricity grid

Electricity grids consist of various components, including cables with different specifications, transformers for voltage conversion, and equipment to respond to grid failures. These assets' dependability and lives, which typically vary from 50 years in high voltage to 25 years in low voltage, are ensured using durable materials like copper, iron, and steel. Around 70% of low-voltage cables in Europe were predicted to be more than 20 years

old in 2020 (Deloitte, 2021). As a result, the technological obsolescence of electric equipment, particularly in medium-voltage and low-voltage lines, might affect the quality of service.

Thus, we can say that electric equipment has a reduced remaining useful life due to ageing. However, this is not the only factor reducing the useful life of assets, which may also vary depending on several factors such as the type of equipment, its design, the quality and frequency of maintenance, and operating conditions. Operating conditions are probably the most relevant factor when facing the new challenges described in Figure 10., since the expected penetration of EVs and the penetration of distributed energy resources may significantly affect the electricity flows into the cables. **Thus, there is a need for new investments in new electric equipment, transformers, and grid lines to cope with ageing and technical obsolescence.**

Self-consumption and distributed energy resources

Increasingly, more energy is being generated locally and connected directly to distribution networks, from solar panels to small power plants. During the last few years, more users have decided to produce their energy, becoming prosumers (i.e., producers and consumers). According to the Annual report from the Spanish Solar Photovoltaics (PV) Union (UNEF, 2022), Solar PV trends in self-consumption have experienced a significant growth rate in Spain, doubling from 2021 to 2022. Notably, the surge in electricity prices in 2022 played a crucial role in driving this increase. However, recent data suggest a decrease in the anticipated growth of self-consumption for 2023, primarily due to a sharp decline in prices, particularly during solar hours (APPA, 2022).

Many users are not willing to be alone in this new self-consumption trend. Instead, they tend to group in energy communities, which can be composed of households, businesses, public buildings, or any other type of energy user. Imagine energy communities as the party in which guests bring their homemade food instead of ordering catering. By leveraging common resources and knowledge, energy communities can reduce their investment risks and obtain reductions in their energy bills, lowering their carbon footprint, while increasing their energy security and resilience. The number of energy communities is reduced, but continuously growing as we can see in the map of energy communities in Spain (IDAE, 2023). Thus, there is a need for investment in and promotion of energy communities, new normative frameworks to facilitate their development as described in (López Prol & Steininger, 2020), and new technologies to enable communication and control of energy.

This situation may be specifically challenging for the DSO, which now must cope with the interconnection of new users generating their energy, thus reducing the electricity demanded by the main grid or distribution grid, with the corresponding decrease in allowed revenues, as described in Figure 8. In addition, the nature of the new users with self-consumption may jeopardise the operation of DSOs, which can result in higher investment and maintenance costs if not properly managed (Hirth et al., 2015). Therefore, it is imperative to implement regulatory mechanisms that can address the potential negative impacts of self-consumption and distributed generation. These mechanisms should focus on promoting stable energy exchange with the grid, thereby mitigating the risk of power congestion in grid nodes and cables. By doing so, the life expectancy of electric assets can be prolonged, ensuring their optimal utilisation and reducing the need for premature replacements.

Electric vehicles integration

Currently, Spain has a reduced fleet of electric vehicles (EVs), which has not reached 100,000 purely electric units (not counting hybrid EVs) in 2021. In addition, the charging infrastructure in 2019 was limited to less than 8,000 public charging points. In Spain, 5 million EVs are expected to be on the roads by 2030, according to the roadmap defined in the PNIEC (MITERD, 2020). To accommodate the growing EV fleet, a comprehensive network of over 340,000 public chargers will be required, as stated in the ANFAC report on EV charging infrastructure deployment in Spain (ANFAC, 2021b). The slow development of the EV market in Spain can be attributed to factors such as complex administrative procedures and concerns about the security of the charging network (ANFAC, 2021a). To overcome these barriers, there is a need for an extensive expansion of EV chargers, driven by manufacturers, energy retailers, and other charging point owners. Effective collaboration among these stakeholders is crucial to enable the widespread deployment of EV chargers and ensure seamless integration with the existing electrical grid infrastructure, facilitated by the DSOs' grid lines.

The presence of high-powered public chargers, with individual ratings exceeding 200 kW, can pose challenges if not effectively monitored, controlled, and managed by charging point owners. Such challenges can subsequently hamper the grid operation of DSOs, which may observe an increase in the utilisation rate of their electric assets.

In this context, DSOs are confronted with a trade-off that requires careful consideration. Option a) involves investing in monitoring the grids to gain insights into the utilisation rate of grid assets located near the charging points. This approach enables DSOs to understand the actual demand and usage patterns, facilitating more informed decision-making. On the other hand, option b) entails extending the power capacity of the existing grid assets through grid reinforcements and the installation of new cables. This proactive measure aims to ensure that the utilisation rate of the cables remains within safe operating conditions, accommodating the increased demand from high-powered chargers.

That is the reason why the RD1125/2021 and part of component 8 within the Spanish Recovery and Resilience Plan are dedicated to digitalisation and the reinforcement of electricity grids to allow the required extension of EV charging infrastructure.

Currently, DSOs lack information about the state of the grid, especially in low-voltage

The integration of distributed energy resources and EVs is expected to grow exponentially in the years to come. **Nevertheless, are DSOs able to observe how the conditions in different parts of the electric grid evolve?** This feature is known as grid observability and, depends on the number of sensors deployed in the grid. In high-voltage grids, since an electric failure may have dramatic costs and consequences, observability is high (the number of sensors and algorithms to estimate the state of the grid is substantial). Such is not the case in medium voltage and, particularly, in low voltage grids, the cables arriving at our households (Song et al., 2017). Thus, we require new digital solutions to understand the state of medium and low-voltage grids. Such understanding provides the gateway for the DSO to carry out a more efficient operation and maintenance, perform better planning, and postpone grid investments, among many other key applications, as it is explained in the first two charts of Figure 11. The plot represents the envisioned power demand in low voltage and the actual measured demand (i.e., more sensors or digitisation), which often will be higher than expected.

Electricity demand reaches maximum installed capacity

The connection of EVs to the electric grids, together with other residential and industrial customers, will undoubtedly increase the overall electricity demand, expected to rise 2% annually from 2017 to 2030, according to (Deloitte, 2021) and the estimations of EVs made in the PNIEC. This situation is described in the third chart of Figure 11, where the power demand of EVs and self-consumption changes the time profile demand in a way that may challenge normal operation and may lead to overloading issues in local areas and certain grid assets.

Figure 11. Flexibility in electricity grids as an opportunity to postpone DSOs grid investments.

Such issues may increase the stress and degradation of electric equipment in electricity grids, whose remaining useful life is reduced. Consequently, new investments will be needed in the distribution grids, as justified by (European Commission, 2022). Such investments would increase the allowed revenues of DSOs and, as a result, increase the electricity bills for consumers. That is the reason we may ask: **are there other options to cope with grid challenges, apart from investing in grid expansion and reinforcement with conventional grid assets?** Here, digitalisation and flexibility provide a crucial alternative.

Sensors provide information to understand the state and utilisation rate of electric grids. Sensors of temperature and noise in electric transformers can provide key information to identify the mechanical and electrical stress of the asset, identifying when is the optimal time in which maintenance actions can be allocated. Furthermore, one sensor located at a certain grid line can allow the DSO to identify at what percentage it is used over its maximum capacity. If the utilisation is close to the maximum (e.g., above 90%), the electricity grids and assets will degrade at a faster pace than if they were used at lower utilisation rates. That is the reason new EVs, and electric demands may accelerate ageing and require new investments if not properly monitored.

Thus, the digitisation of electric measurements and added information from sensors allows DSOs to optimally schedule new investments and increase the capacity of cables or deploy new ones, increasing the maximum capacity. This, yet does not constitute the only choice. Alternatively, we can utilise such information, alongside digital control algorithms, to either

implement energy storage systems to fulfil peaks demand for electricity and store energy when demand is low, or we may advise customers to minimise their consumption of electricity while peak hours. This capability is known as flexibility. Flexible management of electricity grids provides value and benefits both to the DSOs and the users (or stakeholders activating the flexibilities) and will represent a key aspect of the electricity value chain of the future (Deloitte, 2021). Digitalisation supports flexibility by gathering data on the state of electric flows and grid assets, controlling the profile of customers and energy storage technologies, and optimally allocating the activation of flexibility resources, which has been identified as a significant option for the Spanish distribution grids as detailed in (Futured, 2021). **This path of data-intelligence action** is a key aspect of digitalisation where direct benefits can be quantified at the end of the path.

An example of a flexibility source is electric vehicles, which can offer their batteries to inject electricity into the grid when other power generation sources are not available. This concept, known as vehicle-to-grid (V2G) (Yilmaz & Krein, 2013), has the potential to enhance the performance of the electricity grid while creating a new market for EV operation. However, achieving efficient V2G operation necessitates coordination between DSOs, EV owners, and charging point owners. To enable this coordination and optimisation, digitalisation plays a crucial role. In this example, digitalisation enables effective communication among stakeholders, allowing for real-time information on the most advantageous periods for EV charging or discharging. It also enables the forecasting of electricity profiles and EV utilisation, among other valuable applications. By leveraging digital tools and technologies, stakeholders can maximise the economic benefits of V2G operations, optimise grid stability, and support the growth of the EV market.

In the upcoming section, this report explores the wide-ranging benefits of digitalisation in electricity grids, with a focus on flexibility and other evolving digital technologies. By comprehensively examining various digitalisation technologies for distribution grids, we aim to uncover their diverse applications and areas of significant value. This analysis provides insights into how these technologies enhance the efficiency, reliability, and overall performance of distribution grids.

4. Digitalisation of electricity distribution grids: Technologies and Applications

4.1. Digital technologies

 To categorise the digitalisation of distribution grids, a recent study performed by Naturgy, and Comillas University (Spain) (Chaves et al., 2021), provides an overview of the current state and the digital technologies expected to be predominant in the future grids, discussing the potential costs, benefits, and risks. In such a report, the digitalisation technologies most applicable to distribution grids by maturity levels were selected and categorised into four groups: sensors, connectivity, data analytics, and actuators. Sensors and advanced measuring infrastructure (AMI) collect essential data, connectivity enables the communication between grid components, data analytics processes and analyses the collected data, and actuators execute actions based on data insights to optimise grid performance, as described in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Example of big data analytic procedures in distribution grids, from data acquisition to decision-making and value capture. Source: (Zhang et al., 2018).

The previous taxonomy provides an overview of various digital technologies, encompassing data gathering and practical actions within distribution grids. However, to further enhance our understanding, it is crucial to explore how these technologies deliver value to different stakeholders and the nature of that value. In this regard, the work conducted by (Weill & Aral, 2006a) is leveraged to categorise digital technologies into assets providing different value types: **infrastructure, transactional, informational, and strategic**, as described in Figure 13. Such assets might be virtual (e.g., algorithms or computer models) or physical (e.g., hardware and control devices). These asset types are integral to digitalisation efforts, with infrastructure supporting operations, transactional systems facilitating time savings and cost efficiencies, informational assets harnessing data to make better decisions and strategic assets enabling innovation and better long-term planning.

Figure 13. Digitalisation asset types for electric distribution grids. Source: Adapted from the research conducted by (Weill & Aral, 2006b)

Infrastructure digitalisation assets: Sensors and databases

This category of digitalisation technologies refers to the foundational components and systems that support digital operations, such as hardware, networks, and data centres. Infrastructure assets provide the necessary technical resources for digitalisation initiatives and enable the value captured by transactional, informational, and strategic assets. Within this category, sensors, databases, and connectivity represent basic technologies DSOs must have to monitor their grid and transmit the collected data. These assets do not represent fully the end goal of new digitalisation investments, but they constitute part of a set of investments in which infrastructure is the enabler. For instance, without data and databases, artificial intelligence algorithms and cutting-edge algorithms are not able to provide value.

Firstly, sensors play a crucial role in capturing important parameters such as electric current, temperature, and humidity, which are vital for monitoring and managing the grid effectively. An example of measuring devices is smart meters, which accounted for over 99% of meters in Spain in 2021, enabling the shifting of electricity consumption to lower-priced hours, and aligning demand with periods of higher renewable power generation. They are remotely monitored by DSOs in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2016), providing consumption data at frequent intervals. In addition, usage measurement, smart meters facilitate the implementation of new tariffs that incentivise the development of EVs and encourage off-peak charging. Users also gain access to their consumption profiles, promoting transparency and reducing information asymmetries by detecting potential parasite loads.

Smart meters provide real-time monitoring of energy usage, enable dynamic pricing models, allow for remote connection/disconnection of power, empower users with insights for efficient energy management, and automate billing processes, in comparison to the traditional meters. Smart meters play a crucial role in the digitalisation of electricity grids, offering a range of benefits.

In addition to data collection, databases play a crucial role in facilitating digitalisation within organisations. The collected data is transmitted through various communication

means such as fibre optic, Wi-Fi, or mobile communications, and stored within databases. These databases can either be maintained internally within the company or hosted in the cloud, which may be owned by third-party providers like Azure from Microsoft or Google Cloud Platform. Databases provide a structured and secure environment for managing vast amounts of information required for digitalisation initiatives, facilitating collaboration within and beyond the organisation.

In addition to technical assets like sensors, connectivity, and databases, the digital culture of employees plays a crucial role in enabling the successful deployment of digitalisation assets within DSOs. A digital culture encourages employees to embrace new technologies, explore innovative approaches, and collaborate on digital initiatives. This culture of digital readiness and continuous learning empowers employees to effectively utilise databases, extract meaningful insights, and make data-driven decisions. Digital skills are considered key to leverage the benefits of digitalisation, as described in (Chaves et al., 2021).

Informational digitalisation assets: Data analytics

Once data is transmitted to the local server or cloud, it undergoes a series of processing and analysis steps to extract meaningful insights. This corresponds to the informational category of digitalisation assets, where data is transformed into information that is either used by a management system autonomously or by an operator to decide and provide value.

Data analytics involves the application of algorithms and techniques to uncover patterns, predict future behaviour, detect faults or abnormalities, and optimise the operation of distribution grids. By leveraging data analytics, organisations can make data-driven decisions and improve operational processes, as described in (Zhang et al., 2018), who describes data collection devices, data analysis algorithms, .

Data analytics in distribution grids utilises various tools and algorithms to save costs, reduce time, and increase efficiencies. For example, machine learning algorithms can be employed to forecast electricity demand accurately, allowing DSOs to optimise resource allocation and avoid overloading. Additionally, anomaly detection algorithms can identify irregularities in grid behaviour, enabling prompt maintenance and reducing downtime. Grid optimisation algorithms help in minimising losses, improving voltage regulation, and enhancing the overall performance of the distribution network.

Furthermore, data analytics can contribute to load forecasting, enabling DSOs to anticipate peak demand periods and optimise energy distribution accordingly. This reduces the need for costly infrastructure upgrades and improves energy utilisation. Predictive maintenance algorithms can also be utilised to identify equipment failures in advance, enabling proactive maintenance and avoiding costly breakdowns.

Transactional digitalisation assets: Sensors and measuring technologies.

Transactional assets within distribution grids play a significant role in cost savings and decision-making processes, ultimately influencing grid operations. These resources include the systems and procedures used to plan, organise, and carry out transactions, including billing, metering, and customer contacts. Effective use of transactional assets can result in increased operational effectiveness, lower costs, and better decision-making.

In the context of distribution grids, transactional assets can be managed and controlled either by automated actuators or human operators. Actuators, as mentioned earlier, are devices that perform actions to modify or improve grid operations. They can execute commands generated by control algorithms, enabling automated control actions based on predefined rules or conditions. For example, an actuator can automatically adjust voltage levels or switch capacitor banks based on real-time grid conditions, optimising energy flow and minimising losses.

On the other hand, human operators play a vital role in managing transactional assets and making decisions based on grid data and customer interactions. They oversee processes such as billing, customer service, and maintenance scheduling. Human operators possess the expertise to analyse complex data, assess grid performance, and make strategic decisions to improve operational efficiency. For instance, they may identify patterns in consumption data, detect billing anomalies, and propose load management strategies to reduce peak demand.

The interplay between automated actuators and human operators is crucial for effective transactional asset management in distribution grids. Automated actuators provide real-time control actions, responding quickly to grid conditions and optimising operations. Human operators contribute their domain knowledge and decision-making skills to assess system performance, address customer concerns, and make informed decisions that align with grid objectives.

One example of a digital asset within distribution grids is a digital substation. A digital substation represents a modernised and technologically advanced version of a traditional electrical substation, integrating digital technologies and communication systems to enhance its functionality and performance. In a digital substation, traditional analogue devices, such as voltage and current transformers, are replaced with intelligent electronic devices (IEDs). These IEDs incorporate advanced sensors, communication capabilities, and embedded computing power to collect and transmit real-time data about the substation's operation.

The integration of IEDs in a digital substation enables various benefits. First, it enhances the monitoring and control capabilities of the substation by providing more accurate and detailed information about voltage levels, current flows, and equipment status. This allows for better situational awareness and enables timely decision-making to optimise grid operation, allowing the reduction of personnel costs in visiting and checking measurements at substations. Second, the digital substation facilitates condition-based maintenance and asset management. The continuous data collection and analysis capabilities of IEDs enable predictive maintenance, where equipment health can be assessed in real-time, and potential failures or degradation can be identified early. This leads to improved maintenance planning, reduced downtime, and cost savings.

Another example of a transactional asset in the digitalisation of distribution grids is the use of drones. They can be employed for aerial inspections of power lines, substations, and other grid infrastructure, providing visual data, and capturing detailed images of equipment conditions. These inspections can be performed more efficiently and safely compared to traditional manual methods. Drones can also aid in the identification of vegetation encroachment near power lines, enabling proactive vegetation management to prevent outages and enhance grid reliability. The data captured by drones can be transmitted in real-time, allowing grid operators to make informed decisions promptly. Additionally, virtual reality (VR) technology has gained traction as a means of enhancing the operation and maintenance

of distribution grid technicians. Using VR headsets and simulations, technicians can engage in immersive training experiences and practice complex tasks in a controlled virtual environment. This technology enables them to familiarise themselves with equipment, procedures, and potential hazards before undertaking real-world operations. VR can also facilitate remote assistance, allowing experts to provide guidance and support to on-site technicians in real-time, thereby improving efficiency and minimising the risk of errors in connecting new substations or finding anomalous behaviours during operation.

Strategic digitalisation assets: Innovative tools and cybersecurity

Strategic assets encompass digital technologies and capabilities that provide a competitive advantage or drive innovation. This includes emerging technologies, digital business models, intellectual property, and strategic partnerships. Strategic assets are crucial for organisations aiming to gain a competitive edge in the digital landscape.

One emerging concept that holds strategic significance is the use of digital twins. Digital twins refer to virtual replicas or simulations of physical assets, processes, or systems. In the context of power distribution grids, a digital twin represents a real-time digital counterpart of the grid infrastructure, capturing its physical and operational characteristics (Hussen et al., 2023).

Digital twins enable DSOs to gain a deeper understanding of their distribution grids by integrating real-time data from sensors, advanced analytics, and simulation models. This allows for predictive analysis, scenario testing, and optimisation of grid operations. By leveraging digital twins, DSOs can improve asset performance, anticipate, and prevent failures, optimise maintenance schedules, and enhance overall grid reliability and resilience.

However, as DSOs embrace digitalisation and rely heavily on data, the strategic perspective of cyber security becomes paramount (IEA., 2021). Safeguarding the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of data is crucial to ensure the resilience and trustworthiness of digital assets and operations. DSOs must establish robust cyber security measures to protect their data from cyber threats, unauthorised access, and potential disruptions. This involves implementing robust encryption, access controls, intrusion detection systems, and continuous monitoring to identify and mitigate potential cyber risks.

4.2. Digital applications their revenue streams in distribution grids

The digital technologies described above entail both **direct and indirect benefits**, as described in Figure 14. **Directly**, digital technologies can increase energy, time, and resource efficiency, improve decision-making, and provide new products and services for DSOs, where DSOs benefits come from better grid planning and improved operation and maintenance activities. **Indirectly**, digitalisation can act as an **enabler** of decarbonisation, electrification, and democratisation, and offer new economic benefits for energy companies by reducing operating costs, increasing efficiency, and unlocking new business models.

Direct benefits for DSOs

DSOs strategically invest in digital applications to enhance core functionalities across key activity areas. These areas include improved decision-making, new products and services, and enhanced grid planning, operation, and maintenance. Investments impact grid planning,

construction and project management, grid maintenance, grid operation and control, customer relations, and revenue maximisation.

Figure 14. Direct and indirect benefits of DSOs investments within the DSOs' ecosystem.

These areas are essential for ensuring reliable and efficient electricity distribution services, and are described as follows:

 Grid Planning: is an important part of a DSO's activities that implies evaluating and designing the distribution grid to meet changing needs. Advanced data analytics and forecasting algorithms are two examples of how digital technologies are important in this sector. These technologies make it possible to gather and analyse information on grid performance, renewable energy production, and patterns of power usage. DSOs can use this information to influence choices about future network development, infrastructure upgrades, load growth, and capacity requirements. Using a strategic approach, the distribution grid is made to be as efficient as possible to fulfil present and future demand. This results in more dependable and efficient power distribution services for customers.

 Construction and Project Management: Digitalisation plays a crucial role in grid construction and project management, where DSOs put grid infrastructure initiatives into action. By utilising Geographic Information System (GIS) technology, grid planning in construction and project management is one example of how digitalisation can be beneficial. With the aid of GIS, DSOs may produce precise maps and visual representations of their grids that include details about the location, nature, and state of infrastructure elements like transformers, cables, and substations. DSOs may quickly access and analyse information to make knowledgeable decisions during the planning and construction phases by digitising and centralising this data.

 Grid Maintenance: Encompasses the regular inspection, maintenance, and repair of grid assets to ensure their optimal performance, reliability, and longevity. This includes activities such as equipment inspections, preventive maintenance, and addressing faults or failures. One concrete example of how digitalisation benefits grid maintenance in distribution grids is by drones for inspection and monitoring purposes. DSOs can deploy drones equipped with cameras and sensors to conduct aerial inspections of grid infrastructure, such as power

lines, poles, and substations. The drones capture high-resolution images and videos, which are then analysed using advanced image recognition and data analytics algorithms.

Grid Operation and Control: Involves the real-time monitoring, control, and coordination of the distribution grid to maintain stable and efficient operations. This includes activities like load balancing, fault detection and restoration, voltage regulation, and managing grid disruptions. One concrete case of how digitalisation benefits grid operation and control is through the implementation of advanced grid monitoring and control systems. These sensors continuously monitor the grid and provide valuable insights into its operational status. They can monitor grid stability, identify potential issues or abnormalities, and make informed decisions to maintain a reliable and efficient grid operation.

State estimation for distribution grids refers to the process of estimating the real-time state variables (voltage magnitude, phase angle, power flows, etc.) of the distribution network based on available measurements and system models (Ahmad et al., 2018). While state estimation is commonly used by TSOs for monitoring and control, its application in distribution system operations is relatively limited. The use of state estimation technology by DSOs can bring several advantages. Firstly, it enables DSOs to enhance their situational awareness by obtaining accurate and timely information about the state of the distribution grid, thereby facilitating effective monitoring and control. Secondly, state estimation allows for the identification of any anomalies or abnormal conditions in the grid, such as voltage deviations or line overloads, enabling proactive measures to be taken to mitigate potential issues. Moreover, state estimation can contribute to cost reduction for DSOs by reducing the reliance on physical sensors and measurements. Thus, this cost-effective approach enables DSOs to achieve a higher level of observability and system visibility without significant infrastructure investments.

Customer Relations: Focuses on managing customer inquiries, new customers applications providing support, and ensuring customer satisfaction. One example within this area is the deployment of customer self-service portals or mobile applications. Customers may use such platforms to gain accessibility to their electrical usage statistics, payment details, and tailored energy insights. Users can monitor their electricity consumption, analyse their power costs, and make well-informed choices for optimising their consumption patterns.

Revenue Maximisation: Involves strategies and activities aimed at optimising revenue generation for the DSO. This includes the use of digital technologies to explore initiatives such as demand-side management, tariff design, revenue protection, and exploring new revenue streams through value-added services or innovative pricing models. Another example of digital investments and technology that contributes to revenue maximisation for DSOs is the implementation of predictive maintenance systems. By continuously monitoring the condition and performance of grid assets, DSOs can detect potential failures or malfunctions before they occur. This proactive approach allows for timely maintenance interventions, reducing the likelihood of costly equipment failures and associated downtime.

Indirect benefits in distribution grids

The digitalisation of distribution grids brings numerous benefits that extend beyond the direct advantages for DSOs. These benefits have a significant impact on consumers, grid stability, the

scale-up of EVs and DERs, and the emergence of new business models. One key benefit category is the improved experience for consumers. Through digitalisation, consumers gain access to a cleaner and more renewable energy mix. They also enjoy secure and reliable use of EVs and other electric appliances, thanks to enhanced grid planning by DSOs. Smart meters play a crucial role in enabling innovative business models like energy communities, where neighboring households with solar panels and EV chargers come together to rely more on renewables and less on traditional grid operators and energy retailers.

Digitalisation offers consumers the opportunity to actively participate in the energy ecosystem. DSO-developed digital platforms empower consumers to manage their energy consumption and production, allowing them to buy and sell electricity flexibly using their EVs, energy storage systems, and electric appliances. This active participation enables consumers to respond to grid demands and receive financial compensation for their services (PWC, 2022). To navigate the technical complexities of these models, new stakeholders, such as aggregators and energy communities, have emerged to centrally manage and optimise these services. In fact, energy communities, as highlighted by (IDAE, 2019), may provide several advantages. They offer investment opportunities and contribute to the development and acceptance of renewable energy projects. Through demand management and the integration of renewables, energy communities also yield environmental benefits and promote social cohesion, equity, and local job creation.

In summary, the digitalisation of distribution grids not only directly benefits DSOs but also enables consumers to enjoy a cleaner energy mix, actively participate in the energy ecosystem, and fosters the emergence of innovative business models like energy communities. These developments contribute to economic growth and the transition towards a more sustainable energy system.

Investment needs to capture the benefits of digitalisation

Both the public and private sectors must spend heavily if digital technologies are to realise their full promise. However, it is necessary to keep in mind that these expenditures may initially have an influence on customers' power prices. Private sector investment may contribute to promote the use of digital technologies. The power industry will, however, gain eventually from these expenditures thanks to enhanced grid planning, efficient operations, and cutting-edge goods and services for consumers. Along with private sector investment, the public sector is essential in assisting the power sector's digital transformation. The RD1125/2021 exemplifies this by allocating €525 million from the Spanish Recovery and Resilience Plan. This funding aims to foster the application of digital solutions in distribution grids and reinforce electricity grids to accommodate the infrastructure needed for electric vehicle charging. The strategic investment in digitalisation facilitated by the RD1125/2021 is expected to overcome the challenges faced by DSOs and unlock the potential benefits for stakeholders in the electricity sector. It will enhance grid performance, enable efficient integration of renewable energy sources, and contribute to the overall sustainability and resilience of the electricity system.

With a clear understanding of the energy transition challenges, public sector policies, and the role of distribution grids and stakeholders, the report shifts its focus to exploring the specific benefits that the €525 million public investment can bring to different stakeholders.

5. Multi-stakeholder cost benefit assessment of grid digitalisation and modernisation

5.1. DSOs' Investment within the RD1125/2021

According to Section 2, Spain's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) allots a total of €1,050 million in spending, with €500 million coming from the NRRP, for the digitalisation and modernisation of electrical networks for EV charging infrastructure. The CNMC reports for 2021 and 2022, (CNMC, 2022b) and (CNMC, 2022c), include thorough information on the ways in which Spanish DSOs utilised these funds. Table 2 details how much DSOs really spent on the NRRP, as well as how much still must be paid, how much financing from the NRRP was allotted, how much was used, and how much was left over. Notably, during the first year, 2021, a sizable percentage of these funds go unused. Further information is expected to be published, by the CNMC, by the end of 2023.

Table 2. Information about the actual expenditure (in M€) of the NRRP by DSOs per year. Sources: (CNMC, 2022b, 2022c)

CONCEPT \ YEAR	2021	2022	2023	TOTAL
AMOUNT ASSIGNED IN RD 1125/2021 50% FUNDED BY THE NRRPS	454	296	300	1,050
ACTUAL AMOUNT APPLIED FOR BY DSOS	219.286	299 (**)	(*)	(*)
ACTUAL AMOUNT UNUSED	117.357	0	(*)	(*)

(*) Information is expected to be released by the CNMC, by the end of 2023.

(**) Amount over the assigned in RD1125, thus the NRRPs for son DSOs will cover less than 50%, as detailed in (CNMC, 2022c).

Additionally, the CNMC reports provide a breakdown of how these funds are used in different digitalisation technologies and EV charging infrastructure. Table 3 shows the expenditure types for 2021 and 2022, including control rooms, elements for network digitisation and automation, and infrastructure for public EV charging points with a power capacity exceeding 250 kW. Such investments will be the focus of the benefits assessment performed in this paper.

Table 3. Information per expenditure type (in M€) of the funds by DSOs, in 2021 and 2022. Sources: (CNMC, 2022b, 2022c)

EXPENDITURE TYPE	DESCRIPTION AS IN (CNMC, 2022B)	2021	2022	TOTAL
1. DESP_PRTR	Control rooms and control elements necessary for the grid's digitalisation	139.081	171.308	310.389
2. IBO_PRTR	Elements for the digitisation and automation of networks: other technical distribution installations associated with smart grids, telemetry of digital assets, communication systems, and technical management systems.	80.205	125.664	205.869
3. V.E._PRTR	Investments are made to develop and reinforce infrastructure for public electric vehicle charging points with a power capacity over 250 kW, as mandated by regulations.	0	2.631	2.631
TOTAL TO BE SPENT BY DSOS		219.286	299.603	518.889

The DESP_PRTR and IBO_PRTR categories in Table 3 correspond to digitalisation elements, whereas VE_PRTR pertains to the reinforcement of infrastructure for public EV charging points. These expenditure types align with the eligible technologies outlined in Article 7.2 of Royal Decree 1125/2021, which states that investments in digitalisation and automation of

networks necessary for energy transition type 2, as classified in the annex of CNMC Circular 6/2019, are considered eligible for financing with the allocated funds (BOE, 2019). Thus, according to the CNMC Circular 6/2019, the three investment categories: 1. DESP_PRTR 2. IBO_PRTR 3. V.E._PRTR are illustrated in Figure 15, where different technologies associated to each category may be identified.

Figure 15. Infographic of the key technologies to be adopted by DSOs according to (BOE, 2019).

Without further information, the above investments from 2021 to 2022 will be used since information for 2023 is not available. In particular, specific figures regarding the number of sensors, digital substations, and the personnel hours dedicated to new data analytics and software are assumed, according to the main digitalisation technologies highlighted in several studies (Deloitte, 2019) (ABB, 2020) and their expected relevance, interest, and implementation costs. This assumption on the specific investment distribution, aggregated for all DSOs in Spain, is shown below:

- **1. DESP_PRTR: 310.4 M€**
 - 1.1. Modernisation of substations with monitoring and control elements: 50% (155.2 M€)
 - 1.2. Modernisation of control rooms for distribution grids: 40% (124.2 M€)
 - 1.3. Advanced tools for data analytics: 9% (27.9 M€)
 - 1.4. Cyber-security personnel and resources: 1% (3.1 M€)
- **2. IBO_PRTR: 205.9 M€**
 - 2.1. New grid inspection and monitoring elements such as drones: 10% (20.6M€)
 - 2.2. Sensors and monitoring in the grid: 30% (61.8 M€)
 - 2.3. New wireless and wired communication systems: 25% (51.5 M€)
 - 2.4. Supervisory, control and data acquisition systems (SCADA): 20% (41.2 M€)

2.5. Supervisory, control and data acquisition systems in low voltage: 15%(30.9M€)

▪ **3. EV_PRTR: 2.6 M€**

3.1. Investment in new grid capacity extension on transformers and lines to integrate new electric vehicle charging infrastructure: 100% (2.6 M€)

Having defined the DSOs investments, the next step is to assess their potential benefits.

Figure 16. Methodology to assess benefits of smart grid projects. Own elaboration based on (Giordano et al., 2012).

In this study, we adopt a multiple-benefits approach, following the general steps of the EU JRC Guidelines (JRC, 2012) to assess the economic impact of smart grid investments. This is to assess the direct impacts of €1,050 M expenditures on DSOs, and the indirect impacts on other stakeholders such as electricity consumers, EV owners the environment. First, DSOs will be studied, separately, and the benefit categories will be obtained after mapping the different assets and technologies to the DSO’s applications. This aids in the identification of direct and indirect benefits accrued by DSOs and other stakeholders to facilitate later cost-benefit assessment affecting one or several areas and stakeholders. Following such methodology, a benefit assessment will be performed.

5.2. Impacts on distribution system operators (DSOs)

The categorisation of DSOs’ benefits facilitates the identification of individual studies addressing digitalisation and reinforcement of electric infrastructure. Thus, considering the information provided in Subsection 5.1 , an estimation of a set of quantitative effects on DSOs, of investments for a value of 1,050 M€ is detailed below.

Value for DSOs on Grid planning

Grid planning for DSOs refers to the strategic process of designing and developing the electricity distribution network to efficiently meet the growing demand and integrate new electric customers. The strategy involves minimising losses and reducing investment needs by optimising grid infrastructure, implementing advanced technologies for load forecasting and demand response, and enhancing grid management and control systems. In this value category for DSOs, we are focusing on the deployment of digital technologies that provide: 1) new measurements about the grid (since smart meters measurements are often protected by privacy legislations), whose voltages may be unknown in certain parts of the network (especially in

medium voltage and low voltage lines), and 2) new flexibilities to reduce the peak load in grid lines and transformers. Such elements can help to identify areas of inefficiency or congestion and optimise grid operations without significant infrastructure investments. For this purpose, new control devices and measurements are required. Assuming these elements are financed with the investments 1.1., 2.2., 2.3., 2.4., and 2.5., this accounts for a total of approximately 361.1 M€. With these funds, the digital assets that can be derived are:

- New digital substations to operate and control the grid closer to real-time (lower latency) and enhanced advanced measuring infrastructure.
- New sensors in power transformers in medium and low voltage.
- Forecasting tools to estimate the evolution of the capacity utilisation in distribution grid assets.

Several combinations of digital assets may be derived from these unitary costs. However, in line of current trends, we estimate the modernisation and installation of measurements in lines and substations as the key expenditure targets. To estimate costs, the CNMC unitary costs for distribution grids (BOE, 2015) are used as a reference, along with information from various projects. Estimated costs include approximately 47,250 € for low voltage substation modernisation, an educated guess of 100,000 € for medium voltage substation modernisation, and an assumption of 10 M€ for deploying a new high voltage substation (GE, 2021).

Likewise, the development of forecasting and software is generally mostly dependent on technician and data scientist hours. Assuming a data scientist's salary of 50€/h and a one-year implementation period, the unitary cost for a digital forecasting or control tool is expected to be around 100,000 €. Assuming the 361.1 M€ are spent in such technologies, more than 2000 low voltage substation modernisations and 200 medium voltage substation modernisations, and more than 20 new software solutions for DSOs may be performed⁴.

To quantify the impacts of postponing investments and utilising early anomaly detection in distribution grids, it is crucial to highlight their potential as key revenue streams. By investing in new communication and sensor technologies deployed in crucial areas like electric substations, real-time monitoring of electricity flows on connected transformers and cables becomes possible. This monitoring facilitates immediate assessment of cable and transformer capacity utilisation. As the perspectives of growing future demand for electricity show (REE, 2021), it may become necessary to reinforce or upgrade the capacity of these assets in the upcoming years. Therefore, postponing investments can offer significant value to DSOs in Spain. According to projections, DSOs are expected to spend over 7,300 M€ on reinforcing or upgrading the distribution grid from 2020 to 2030 (Deloitte, 2021). Postponing a portion of these investments can allow them to free up cash that can be utilised to further modernise their systems and subsequently invest in new innovative projects. The concept of postpone investment by reducing the capacity utilisation of assets is represented in Figure 17.

⁴ In future studies, this estimation must be obtained through collaboration with stakeholders and surveys of different projects related to the digitalisation of distribution grids within DSOs' plans.

Figure 17. Electric assets on distribution grids and their expected capacity utilisation with increased electrification. Source: own elaboration and the Electrical Engineering Portal, respectively.

Considering the effects of digital technologies for increasing the transparency on the state of the electric assets and their utilisation, two scenarios can be derived:

- **Scenario 1:** When measured, lines and transformers are less loaded than expected. In this case, potential investments can be postponed to future years, easing the cash flows of DSOs, and allowing them to allocate those funds to other activities. The benefits of postponing investments need to be compared with investments in new digital applications.
- **Scenario 2:** When measured, lines and transformers are more loaded than expected. This situation can lead to cable overloads and increase the probability of component failures. Therefore, it is crucial to identify the most heavily loaded elements to prioritise investments and minimise future grid failures.

In relation to scenario 1, digital substations and flexibility can offer a solution to cope with high peak loads in substations, common situation in scenarios with high renewable penetration. According to ABB, a technology manufacturer, digital substations offer several advantages. They enable transactive trading, reducing peak demand by 8%. Additionally, they provide dynamic rating⁵ of cables and transformers, allowing for a 5-20% increase in capacity by monitoring asset conditions and allocating load safely. Digital substations can also optimise losses and voltage profiles for EVs and PV storage systems integration (ABB, 2019). Assuming the power capacities of low voltage and medium voltage substations of around 2 MVA and 20MVA of capacity, respectively, taking the values of 10 % capacity increase from ABB, 800MW of new capacity can be developed (Electrical Engineering Portal, 2022). In this case, it is estimated that new capacity can represent the integration of 174,000 new households of 4.6 kW of installed power which, with an average consumption per household of 4,000kWh and a DSOs access tariff of 0.06 €/kWh, may result in 41.7 M€ of yearly revenues for DSOs only in capacity additions.

The previous estimation is supported by the initial numbers given by one of the DSOs, I-DE, on this matter, which is estimated in 400MW (i-DE, 2023). This may represent the integration of more than 87,000 new households of 4.6 kW which, with an average consumption per household of 4,000kWh and a DSOs access tariff of 0.03 €/kWh, may result in more than 10

⁵ For more information about dynamic rating of electric assets, kindly read (Dong, 2021).

M€ of yearly revenues. Additionally, regarding grid resilience, a better planning due to digitalisation can foresee areas where natural disasters may be more likely to happen, mitigating their effects.

Regarding scenario 2, when identifying most loaded cables and prioritising investments, the overall performance of quality of supply and security of supply can be improved. Thus, interruptions can be avoided. By doing so, costs and improve operational efficiency, reduce operational costs, and ensure a smooth integration of new electric customers into the existing grid infrastructure. Additionally, regarding grid resilience, a better planning due to digitalisation can foresee areas where natural disasters may be more likely to happen, mitigating their effects.

Besides digitalisation, part of DSO's expenditures will be dedicated to grid planning and the construction of new capacity which can be used to allocate, among other customers, new 250kW EV charging (CNMC, 2022c) points. DSOs are not the operators or developers or charging points, but they are identified as the entity which must provide with enough power capacity to facilitate the connection of the charging points.

Construction and project management (PM)

Digital technologies such as Virtual reality (VR), integrated with comprehensive databases on electric assets, failures, and environmental conditions, holds significant promise for enhancing construction and project management in distribution grids. By harnessing VR's immersive visualisation and simulation capabilities, stakeholders can make informed decisions, optimise project plans, and proactively identify potential issues. This contributes to streamlined construction processes, reduced rework, and improved project outcomes. Access to comprehensive information on electric assets, historical failures, and environmental conditions facilitates superior planning and resource allocation. By visualising and analysing asset data within a virtual environment, maintenance teams can proactively identify maintenance needs, schedule preventive measures, and optimise asset performance. This translates into improved reliability, reduced downtime, and cost savings.

In the context of Spanish distribution grids, the adoption of VR technology, in conjunction with integrated databases, has been estimated to yield annual savings exceeding €10 million (Gridspertise, 2022). These savings accrue from optimised project plans, streamlined construction processes, enhanced collaboration, improved training, and proactive asset management. The value provided by VR and databases resides in their potential to transform project management practices, drive efficiency, and ultimately contribute to the successful execution of distribution grid projects.

Grid maintenance

Adequate maintenance is of utmost importance for DSOs to increase the useful lives of assets, which is particularly critical in Spain given the current age structure of distribution grids, especially low-voltage ones. However, DSOs face challenges in locating failures and promptly responding to them. In this context, the emergence of digital solutions has revolutionised the grid maintenance process, offering numerous benefits. By harnessing the power of data, DSOs can shift from reactive to predictive maintenance strategies. Through advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms, they can analyse historical failure data, environmental conditions, and asset performance indicators to identify patterns and predict potential failures.

This proactive approach enables DSOs to prioritise maintenance efforts, allocate resources effectively, and address issues before they escalate. One significant advantage of digital solutions is the ability to remotely monitor and diagnose assets. With the integration of sensors and IoT devices, DSOs can gather real-time data on asset performance, condition, and health parameters. This remote monitoring capability reduces the need for physical inspections, saving significant person-hours of work and associated costs. DSOs can remotely assess the health of assets, detect anomalies, and trigger maintenance actions only when necessary, optimising resource utilisation and minimising downtime.

Moreover, digital solutions facilitate the optimisation of maintenance processes through automation and intelligent algorithms. By leveraging historical data, maintenance schedules, and asset conditions, algorithms can optimise maintenance plans, prioritising critical assets and optimising the allocation of maintenance resources. This results in improved operational efficiency, reduced costs, and enhanced reliability of the distribution grid. With data analytics, DSOs can perform predictive maintenance avoiding inspections and saving many person-hours of work. According to (Chaves et al., 2021), the potential cost reduction in maintenance is estimated at 21%. Assuming with the NRRP funds DSOs can achieve 20% of such potential, this may represent more than 43 M€ for the total Spanish distribution sector yearly, considering the allowed operation and maintenance costs for the three largest DSOs in 2019 was 1,044 M€ (MITECO, 2022).

Grid operation and control

DSOs can significantly enhance the quality of their power supply by embracing digitalisation and implementing automated control systems within their substations. When integrating various elements of automation and control, DSOs can optimise maintenance processes and effectively plan their grid operations. This becomes crucial as DSOs strive to seamlessly integrate new renewable energy sources and self-consumers into their electric grids, while ensuring the continuity and reliability of power supply without requiring substantial infrastructure investments.

Automated control systems implemented in substations provide real-time monitoring and management of flows and voltages within the grid. Through the deployment of advanced sensors and intelligent devices, DSOs can continuously gather data on electricity consumption, voltage levels, and other important parameters. This data is then subjected to analysis and processing using sophisticated algorithms, optimising grid operations. For example, during instances of excess renewable energy generation, automated control systems can intelligently regulate power flow, ensuring efficient utilisation and preventing grid congestion. By dynamically adjusting voltage levels and redirecting power flows, DSOs can maintain grid stability and minimise energy losses.

Moreover, automated systems have the capability to detect anomalies or potential failures, triggering proactive maintenance actions. This proactive approach minimises downtime and enhances the overall reliability of the system. It is important to note that the benefits of digital applications extend beyond specific areas within an organisation, impacting multiple activities simultaneously and at different time intervals. For instance, implementing new controls can alleviate cable overload in the present, which in turn may influence future electric asset replacements, ultimately avoiding the need for investing in new assets. Minimising failures with smart substations control and operations can provide significant benefits to DSOs. In fact,

these can reduce considerably the duration of failures, which ultimately affect revenues maximisation.

DSOs also face the concern of cyber-attacks as digital substations and interconnected systems become more prevalent in the energy sector. However, digitalisation can serve as a crucial tool in mitigating these risks and ensuring the secure operations of DSOs. It is essential for DSOs to invest in digital substations and robust cyber-security software to safeguard their infrastructure and counter cyber threats effectively. Integrating cyber-security measures into digital substations helps address vulnerabilities that arise from interconnected networks and data exchange. DSOs may create secure communication channels and protect their vital infrastructure from illegal access by putting modern security protocols and encryption techniques into practise.

One of the primary concerns is the potential financial impact of a data breach. A single data breach can result in significant financial losses, as indicated by studies conducted by (IBM, 2022), which estimate costs exceeding €4.7 million. Moreover, the time and resources required to remediate the breach can be substantial, leading to the loss of approximately 50 person-hours. Therefore, investments in cyber-security infrastructure and practices become essential in mitigating these risks. DSOs may proactively identify and respond to cyberthreats by putting in place strong security measures including firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and continuous monitoring. These precautions aid in guarding against unauthorised access, data breaches, and potential grid outages.

Revenue maximisation

Digitalisation in grid planning, maintenance, control, project management and customer service bring new customers and reduces existing costs, which contributes to DSO profits. Additionally, in Spain, the market regulator incentivises DSOs to reduce electric losses, fight against energy fraud, and improve the quality of service. This is done by a set of rewards and penalties according to the kWh of energy loss and the frequency and minutes of customer interruptions.

Power losses are an important factor of efficiency in distribution grids. The older the assets are and the higher fraud and interruptions due to failures and maintenance, the higher the electricity losses. Thus, DSOs are incentivised to reduce losses in every regulatory period. Here, using new assets, better maintenance, and digitalisation, they can reduce grid losses, whose yearly incentives and penalties reached €18 M for I-DE (Iberdrola Group) and €-4.9 for e-distribution (Endesa Group), due to their evolution in electricity losses. Quality is also a relevant factor for electricity customers, and thus for the regulator. That is the reason why a set of incentives and penalties are established to guarantee a suitable and rising level of quality of supply. These incentives can range from 2% to -3% of allowed revenues to incentivise improvements or penalise worsening quality. For instance, I-DE received 2018 around €3.5 M due to quality improvements. Likewise, due to data analytics and AI, *e-distribución* was able to recover 795,000 MWh in 2021, equivalent to 240,000 households' electricity consumption (Endesa, 2022). This is estimated to represent more than €9 M for the DSO, recovered annually by grid charges. In addition to this amount, the regulator incentivises such energy recovery with 20% of the €9 M recovered by grid charges, with a total of 1.8 M€. Assuming these 9 M€+1.8 M€ (10.8M€) can be achieved at least by the three major DSOs, whose investment in digitalisation is higher, this benefit accounts for a total of **32.4 M€**.

The deployment of digital technologies in various aspects of the power grid, such as grid planning, maintenance, operation and control, project management, and customer service, is expected to have a lasting impact. These digital advancements offer significant benefits in terms of optimising grid infrastructure, improving project outcomes, enhancing maintenance practices, and enabling efficient grid operation. Nevertheless, it is critical to admit that the realisation of these benefits may require ongoing investments for the maintenance of digital technologies, which may face the challenge of early technical obsolescence. As technology rapidly evolves, digital tools and platforms may become outdated, necessitating regular updates and replacements to remain at the forefront of innovation. This ongoing maintenance and adaptation to prevent technological obsolescence may incur additional costs for power grid operators.

One key aspect to consider is the extension of benefits over time. The implementation of digital solutions in grid planning can result in optimised infrastructure and identification of inefficiencies, leading to reduced infrastructure investments. These advantages are anticipated to last for more than 15 years, demonstrating the long-term advantages of digitalisation in this field. Similarly, it is anticipated that during the next four to five years, virtual reality technology, which improves construction and project management, will become more generalised and adopted in this market. Processes are streamlined, project results are improved, and stakeholder cooperation is encouraged through this technology. The general advantages of virtual reality technology are projected to last long after its first application, notwithstanding the possibility that it will continue to develop.

However, it is essential to recognise that the maintenance of digital technologies introduces additional considerations. While digital solutions like predictive maintenance and remote monitoring can increase asset lifespan and reduce operational costs, they require ongoing investments to ensure their effectiveness.

In conclusion, the benefits of digitalisation in grid planning, maintenance, operation and control, project management, and customer service are expected to have a lasting impact. However, the maintenance of digital technologies and addressing technical obsolescence present ongoing challenges that require continuous investment. While the benefits of digitalisation extend over an extended period and can significantly reduce operational costs, it is crucial for power grid operators to remain vigilant in managing the maintenance and evolution of digital infrastructure to ensure long-term sustainability and maximise the advantages offered by digital advancements.

Results: Direct impacts on DSOs

Figure 18 illustrates a breakdown of the estimated benefits resulting from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) funds for distribution system operators. The benefits are disaggregated based on key functionalities, highlighting the diverse areas where improvements and advancements are expected by the deployment of digitalisation technologies.

Besides DSOs, the €1,050 M expenditures enable a wide range of activities, services, and benefits for other different stakeholders. Such benefits are detailed in next.

5.3. Impacts on the integration of electric vehicles and renewable energies

Regarding the limited funds dedicated to it on the NRRP of around 2.6M€ ([3.EV PRTR](#)), and according to several projects of EV charging points deployment, the incremental capacity that may be dedicated to EV charging stations could be approximately ⁶, 53MW. This calculation has been performed considering the cost of new transformers in medium voltage €/MW for 36kV-1kV substation as 16,358 €/MW, according to the CNMC (CNMC, 2014), together with a safety factor of three to account for expenses in lines and field work.. Assuming a high peak charging power (i.e., fast charger) of 35 kW, 1,513 new EVs could be charged at the charging stations with the described investments. These numbers will be higher when digitalisation is adopted by the owners of the charging stations, having the potential to avoid potential grid congestion (Deloitte, 2021).

⁶ Relevant categories for finding information on power transmission capacity of medium voltage cables include IEEE and IEC standards, cable manufacturer datasheets, and electrical engineering textbooks on power systems and electrical distribution.

New chargers will enable a positive feedback loop for new EV owners and, consequently, the deployment of more EV charging points. Digitalisation also contributes to the allocation of more grid capacity for chargers, which could be smoothly integrated under a digitised, monitored, and optimally controlled grid.

A similar situation occurs with the allocation of new distributed renewable energy sources which, according to the calculations from Iberdrola (i-DE, 2023), the RD 1125/2021 funds will allow the integration of 1 GW of electricity generation capacity and a net saving of 2.6 million tonnes of CO₂ per year. In this sense, our calculations show more conservative results. If this were the new renewable capacity that could be integrated into the grid of each of the three major distributors, this new aggregate capacity (3 GW of renewables) operating 30% of the time would generate 7,884 GWh. In addition, 7,884 GWh produced with fossil fuels (basically combined cycle) and considering the typical emission factor of a combined cycle plant in Spain (0.37 tCO₂/MWh), this results in 2.9 M tonnes of CO₂ avoidable per year. To this should be added the tonnes avoided by new electric vehicles associated with the expansion of the recharging network induced by the PRTR subsidies, but as we have seen, this induced expansion is very limited so far.

Electric vehicles and renewables provide a set of environmental and social benefits for consumers and society, ranging from improved Spanish energy security and reduced urban pollution and environmental footprint. Regarding energy dependence, in 2021, Spanish fossil fuel imports accounted for 70.4 % of the total primary energy consumed (MITECO, 2023). Considering the effect of funds on different DSOs, in a scenario with 3 new GW of renewables operating 30% of the time, we could replace approximately 7,884 GWh of electricity produced by fossil fuels, reducing the overall Spanish energy dependence by more than 1%. As an additional and key advantage of renewables, such electricity of 7,884 GWh coming from fossil fuels and natural gas would represent, considering an efficiency of combine cycle power plants of 50% (MITECO, 2016), 15,768 GWh (gas). This, with a day ahead price of natural gas in Spain from a day of 27€/MWh (MIBGAS, 2023), 425.7 M€ could be saved by the integration of these 3GW of new renewables.

This illustrates the fact that specific investments in grids, digitalisation, and EVs have an actual impact on overall energy security and may have substantial potential in the upcoming years.

5.4. Impacts on electricity consumers

The digitalisation of distribution grids in Spain brings about several advantages, including access to a more renewable and clean energy mix and the secure and reliable use of electric vehicles and domestic appliances such as electric boilers or heat pumps. These benefits are made possible through enhanced grid planning by DSOs, resulting in a reduction in the number and duration of power interruptions.

For example, according to (Deloitte, 2019), the digitalisation investments deployed in the smart grid project in Bilbao, between 2010 and 2016, have reduced local interruptions downtime by 60%, the cost of inspections by 20% and technical losses in the grid by 10%.

If taking the figure of 60% of local interruptions to a global level, we can quantify the potential of smart grid projects among different DSOs using the cost of energy not supplied. The quantification of the value of energy not supplied, known as the Value of Lost Load (VoLL), has been a crucial area of research in justifying the adoption of digitalisation technologies to

enhance grid operation and security. A comprehensive study conducted by (Linares & Rey, 2013) estimated the VoLL for different regions and economic activities in Spain. The VoLL values ranged from 0 to 5 €/kWh for agriculture, transport, services, and manufacturing sectors, while exceeding 35 €/kWh for the construction sector. For the purposes of this discussion, an average value of 3 €/kWh can be considered. Now, let us assess the impact on the Spanish distribution grids in terms of the number of interrupted hours for customers. According to the data published in the MITECO about the quality of electricity supply in Spain, the average duration of equivalent interruption (NIEPI) per installed power is around 0.7 hours of equivalent interruption per year in urban areas (MITECO, 2020). Thus, considering the installed capacity of distribution in Spain was 93,895 MVA in 2020 (Red Eléctrica de España, 2021) and the 3€/kWh of VoLL, a preliminary estimation of the VoLL is made on: 197 M€. If avoiding 60% of such costs (considering the RD1125/2021 funds will only be a part of the solution), smart technologies can save **118 M€** yearly in improving the whole system reliability.

Likewise, regarding final customers, digital platforms are a crucial digital technology that can provide significant benefits, while also ensuring efficient DSO operations and creating opportunities for new business models and consumer participation in the electricity market. These platforms, developed by DSOs, serve as a gateway for consumers to engage in various projects such as self-consumption and EV charging. They promote transparency, empowering consumers to actively manage their consumption and production within the updated electricity grid infrastructure, as highlighted in a recent report on self-consumption and consumer roles in electric systems (PWC, 2022).

By utilising these platforms, consumers can participate in flexible electricity trading with the grid. They can leverage electric vehicles, energy storage systems, and electric appliances as active components to respond to grid demands by adjusting their electricity consumption, either decreasing or increasing it as needed. In exchange for providing this service, consumers receive payments. The deployment of such digital platforms is explicitly mandated by RD1125, which also requires the implementation of digital programs aimed at improving the quality of customer service.

6. Conclusions and future research

This study has examined the impact of digitalisation on Spanish distribution networks, focusing on the benefits. In particular, we have assessed the role of Royal Decree 1125/2021, which aims to promote the digitisation of distribution networks and electric vehicle charging infrastructure. The funds provided through this regulation offer DSOs a direct opportunity to digitise their networks and invest in new technologies. These investments are crucial to unlocking electrification trends and achieving greater efficiency, resilience and future-proofing. However, the regulated monopoly nature of distribution networks often hinders the willingness of DSOs to invest in modernisation or to be as innovative as other sectors. These funds are therefore a positive initiative to address this problem.

However, despite the positive aspects of this initiative, certain shortcomings in its implementation can be identified. Concerns in this regard include the possibility that numerous benefits acquired by DSOs as private companies represent a direct transfer of resources from the regulator. At the same time, reliance on ad-hoc funds and solutions, such as subsidies and project allocations, may hinder or mask the underlying problem of the need to reform distribution networks and the role of DSOs, as well as their remuneration regime. To address this, the reform should include special remuneration for digitisation assets, which face different technical obsolescence and higher risks than conventional assets such as grid lines and electricity transformers. Another aspect to highlight is the remuneration of DSOs in PRTRs, which tends to benefit larger companies, creating a digital divide between larger and smaller DSOs.

Therefore, in order to ensure a more equitable allocation of funds, an auction system with equal participation for all DSOs and a project selection based on a cost-benefit analysis could be used. Furthermore, the inclusion of EV charging infrastructure investments within these funds should be carefully examined as the use of these subsidies to enable the installation of EV charging infrastructure has so far been practically non-existent, according to information from the CNMC. Consequently, in order to optimise the results of digitisation and grid modernisation, several issues need to be addressed:

- Regulatory schemes should incentivise digital investments while ensuring a suitable quality of supply. Disincentives linked to reductions and interruptions should be strengthened, and the value of undistributed energy should be integrated into DSOs' investment planning.
- Additional metrics should be implemented to supplement conventional quality and losses metrics. These metrics should capture the degree of digitalisation, observability, and smartness of DSOs' operations and planning, as supported by (E.DSO et al., 2021) and (Chaves et al., 2021).
- Regulations should facilitate data sharing from grid monitoring while safeguarding user privacy, enabling the development of new business models for the energy transition.
- Reforms are necessary to reduce bureaucratic barriers and increase governmental resources dedicated to facilitating the integration and connection of electric chargers. The current situation in Spain, where the process to operate a charging point can take between 24 and 32 months, resulting in frozen investment of 6,000 €M (Portal Movilidad, 2023) requires immediate attention and necessary reforms.

Despite these concerns about funds to support digitalisation, this study has helped to demonstrating the potential of digitalisation on distribution grids and the advantages it may give to numerous stakeholders on a national scale. This is a initial phase towards assessing the effects of technological advancement, which has become a fundamental driver of increased digital technology use and competitiveness.

Yet, there are a few limitations in this investigation which deserve further investigation. We acknowledge the necessity of exploring and strengthening the quantitative assessment of digitalisation implications by thorough, model-based, and systems-based cost-benefit studies. These evaluations should consider the complexity of digital technology, the interconnectedness of tangible and intangible assets, the extensive causal chains of impacts, and the holistic approach. By addressing these aspects, we can enhance our understanding of the benefits of digitalisation and make informed decisions to optimise grid modernisation efforts and promote the widespread adoption of digital technologies.

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